

DOES EXPERIENCE AND MORAL UPBRINGINGS AFFECT A PERSON'S
PROPENSITY TO BLOW THE WHISTLE?

by

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Does Experience and Morals/Values Affect A Person's Propensity to Blow the Whistle?

Abstract

This study examines whether a person's propensity to blow the whistle is influenced by factors such as work experience or being raised in a good household. This study examines whether the type of household someone was raised in (good vs. bad) or their level of experience (inexperienced vs. experienced) influences their propensity to blow the whistle. The results of this study indicated that neither factor influences a person's propensity to blow the whistle. It did little to none in influencing a person's tendency to blow the whistle.

Keywords: Whistleblowing, propensity, correlation, significance

Data availability: Contact the authors

I. Introduction

Whistleblowing is often a delicate subject to discuss. There are infinite possibilities that might influence a person to blow the whistle or not. They might be afraid of retaliation, or if a person does decide to blow the whistle, they might be ignored, and the boss might "sweep it under the rug." Frequently, there are many high-profile cases where whistleblowers would blow the whistle on a company for any wrongdoings. One of the main reasons whistleblowing is an interesting topic to study is why certain people are more prone to blow the whistle if they encounter any wrongdoings, while others are just idly complying and ignoring any misdeeds committed by the company. Another motivation for studying the propensity to blow the whistle is that many college students are entering the workforce. These recent college graduates will enter the workforce and encounter situations where they will deal with scenarios to decide whether to blow the whistle. This topic needs to be explored further to determine which factors may influence a person's propensity to blow the whistle or not.

This study will be focused on a person's propensity to blow the whistle or not. We will be studying factors such as whether work experience and growing up in a good household with

great values do play a factor in influencing a person's propensity to blow the whistle or not. The main research question is whether factors and reasons such as work experience and growing up in a good household with great values influence a person's propensity to blow the whistle or not if they encounter any wrongdoings committed by the company during their tenure there.

In this paper, we investigated factors such as work experience and whether growing up in a good household may influence a person's propensity to blow the whistle or not if encountered with a scenario of seeing a company committing wrongdoings. We have to look at each variable closely because frequently, there are many reasons why many would consider blowing the whistle on their company. For example, a person's experience might decide whether they decide to blow the whistle on the company. They might regret doing so because it may ruin their reputation in the company, and they may not have any career opportunities left. On the other hand, if the person is relatively new, like a college graduate entering the company, they may have other options left and might feel encouraged to blow the whistle. Another reason that we might have to examine these variables further is that, for example, growing up in a good household with good values might influence a person to blow the whistle or not. If, for example, they did grow up in a household with good morals and values, then they might feel compelled to blow the whistle because it is the right thing to do. On the other hand, if they grew up in a poor household with no good values or morals, they might not desire to blow the whistle, considering that they do not feel that it is morally right to do so, and they would rather keep it to themselves.

In the research, we gave a group of students a survey, constructed via Qualtrics to analyze students' propensity to blow the whistle, given hypothetical scenarios. For example, each student was given a scenario and was given variables. These variables included being an experienced worker or a new hire, a person being raised with good morals and values or not. Then the Qualtrics survey asked them if that particular person saw something nefarious committed by the company. Later, students were given questions to answer whether they would

blow the whistle if they were in their shoes. Students will also use a scale between 1-7, with one being unlikely and seven being very likely to answer the given questions.

The results did indicate that there were no solid indicators or reasons as to why some people were willing to blow the whistle or not. Most students were indifferent when answering the questions, and the results indicated that work experience and being raised in a good household were not strong reasons to sway people in blowing the whistle or not.

This research paper's contributions are that it will give other researchers things that they can learn from. For example, they will know that work experience and being raised in a good household are not factors to look into when measuring a person's propensity to blow the whistle or not. Another contribution that other people may make would be that other researchers will look into other factors in seeing why some people are willing to blow the whistle while others are reluctant.

The rest of the paper is organized as a typical research paper. We will have literature review/hypothesis development, experimental designs and methods, results, and conclusions. Like experimental designs and techniques, these main parts are broken down into mini sections such as design/participants, tasks, independent variables, dependent variables, and manipulation checks.

II. Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

This project seeks to answer the question of how does a person's level of work experience (i.e., are they experienced or inexperienced) or does the presence of a good upbringing (i.e., mentioning that they grew up in a good household or not) influence people's propensity to blow the whistle? Whistleblowing definition is "current or former organization members or persons whose actions are under the control of the organization, who lacks authority to prevent or stop the organization's wrongdoing" (Near and Miceli 1985).

Whistleblowing is often considered a hard thing to do because "...whistleblowers are often

publicly viewed as saviors or snitchers" (Campbell 2013). For example, one of the recent headlines that involved a whistleblowing case involved a woman named Rebekah Jones. Ron Desantis accused Rebekah Jones of not reporting false data about COVID-19 in Florida (MSNBC). She decided to disclose the correct data because she hated how the government did not care for their people (MSNBC). Unfortunately, she was terminated and was targeted by officers and the government (MSNBC). This is one of many examples, why people are terrified to report and blow the whistle.

There were a few notable whistleblowing cases when people did come forward and ultimately ruined their reputation. One notable whistleblowing case was the Worldcom Case. The Worldcom Case was one of the most prominent cases of fraud and whistleblowing. According to Peter Yeoh, 2014, the Worldcom Case could have easily been prevented...in some significant ways provided that some workers disclosed their concerns they had at the early stages" (Peter Yeoh, 2014). Many workers at the time were conflicted "...between institutional loyalty and moral conscience to report wrongdoings" (Peter Yeoh 2014). They were conflicted because, on the one hand, they could be ostracized from their jobs if they came forward with any information implicating the company. The WorldCom Case is so notable that a woman came forward with incriminating information (CFO.com). The company later fired her, and thus the wrongdoings that the company tried to hide became public. She decided to come forward with the information and made herself the whistleblower who blew the report that implicated the company. No one from the accounting world, especially auditing, decided to hire her again because she was a whistleblower and a snitch. Unfortunately, she could not work in any accounting firm again; she made a career speaking about her events tied to the Worldcom Case (CBA Speakers Bureau). This case highlights the implications of coming forward and being a whistleblower.

We wanted to examine whether factors would make a person decide to bring information that might be considered illegal, immoral, or illegitimate. Ideally, multiple variables would

influence a person's propensity to blow the whistle. For example, Sims-Keenan research, they were researching factors that would affect a person's predisposition to blow the whistle externally. According to Sims-Kennan's study, several factors did cause a person to blow the whistle externally. One example was that "...external whistleblowing would be positively related to supervisor support for external whistleblowing" (Sims-Kennan 1998). Their findings were that "...the perceived supervisor support is significantly related to the choice to blow the whistle...in addition, supervisor support was found to be a significant predictor of external whistleblowing" (Sims-Kennan 1998).

Sims-Kennan's research determined that multiple variables influence a person's propensity to blow the whistle. Some of their theories, such as that external whistleblowing does affect a person's predisposition to blow the whistle externally, were the significant indicators for workers to come forward. Some theories such as "...external whistleblowing would be positively related to organizational commitment" found not to correlate "...or significantly related to external whistleblowing" (Sims-Kennan 1998). Multiple factors influence a person's propensity to blow the whistle.

For this research project, we were determined to find two specific variables: work experience and the fact that a person grew up in a good household influences a person's propensity to blow the whistle. From previous research, other correlations did influence a person to blow the whistle externally. Still, we desired to analyze their propensity and influence to blow the whistle whether or not one or two of the variables did influence a person to blow the whistle. We desired to pinpoint the specific impacts and know whether these factors affect a person to blow the whistle.

For this project, we predicted that factors make a person's propensity to blow the whistle higher. Through this research, if work experience is present, we would expect people not to blow the whistle, especially if they were working longer. If moral upbringings are present, then people might act better and will have a stronger desire to blow the whistle compared to others

who are not raised with good moral upbringings. If both moral upbringing and work experience are present, people might desire to blow the whistle more; although they might lose their job, it is morally right to do so. Some factors will convince people to blow the whistle.

III. Experimental Design and Method

Design and Participants

For this study, we are testing two independent variables and determining whether or not these factors influenced a person to blow the whistle. The participants in this study are CSUF business students in a professor's accounting class. In total, 100 participants completed the survey on Qualtrics, but 50 students failed to answer the manipulations correctly; thus, we had to exclude 50 participants from the research.

Task

The task was that CSUF students majoring in business were given the job of answering a survey. An example of the Qualtrics survey is found in the appendices on page 9. The survey was set up using Qualtrics. Students would be given a random survey and answer the questions to the best of their ability. The survey will initially feature Casey Greenshade. Depending on the survey, she will either be an experienced senior analyst or a newly hired analyst, randomly generated for each participant. Casey Greenshade will encounter an issue where she must decide whether or not to blow the whistle. The survey will also randomly generate the other independent variable of whether or not Casey was raised in a good household or not.

Independent Variables

There were two independent variables in this study. The first variable was work experience (high experience versus low experience). The first independent variable was used in this study, mentioning Casey Greenshade in a hypothetical scenario of being an experienced analyst versus an inexperienced analyst. The other independent variable was the mentioning of being raised in a good household or not. With this independent variable, it was used in the study

as stating whether or not Casey Greenshade was raised in a good household or not. The purpose of testing these independent variables was to see whether they influence a person's propensity to blow the whistle. All CSUF business students took part in the survey and were in Professor Chen's accounting course. They read the case, and the case did include two independent variables. These two independent variables are randomly generated due to the setup on Qualtrics.

Dependent variables

The dependent variable would be other factors outside of the experienced vs. inexperienced and the mentioning of a good household or not. For example, it could be whether or not to report the incident mentioned in the case internally or externally. For the survey on Qualtrics, we used a scale of 1-7 to measure these factors, the dependent variables. Surveyors would be asked to rate different scenarios related to the case 1-7, with one strongly disagreeing and seven strongly agreeing.

Manipulation checks

At the beginning of the study, when participants opened the survey on Qualtrics, they were asked two questions to make sure that the participants read. If they answered correctly, the answers that followed would be counted in the survey. If they do not answer them correctly, many students will be removed when we check the survey. The two questions that many of the participants were asked were:

1. {Yes, No) Did the case say Casey was recently hired?
2. (Yes, No) Did the case mention that Casey came from a good household that emphasized good moral values and honesty?

In total, 50 participants answered the questions correctly, but there were only 50 people that answered the questions incorrectly, which forced us to delete and not include them in the study.

IV. Results

Our results indicated that people's propensity to blow the whistle was not influenced by the level of work experience and good morals. The results demonstrated that these two independent variables studied were not the main reasons why a person might choose to blow the whistle or not. Also, the results were limited due to people's participation being on the web rather than in person due to the constraints of COVID, and we asked students in business to participate rather than recent graduates or actual business professionals. Therefore, it might be worth investigating further and narrowing down the culprits in influencing a person's propensity to blow the whistle in the future. We also might need to conduct a better way to gather our data and not be bound by the limitations mentioned earlier regarding COVID.

Potential Covariates and Initial Analysis

A Qualtrics survey was conducted, and when participants received a link to participate. They were given numerous questions to answer. Some of these questions that have been asked were potential covariates at the end of the Qualtrics survey. These questions were mainly demographic questions that included asking participants about their gender, education, work experience, etc. Also, there were other debriefing questions designed to determine different factors that might have influenced a person's propensity to choose how they answer these questions in a certain way.

For example: How much did the potential for a reduced sentence influence your decision to report?

Participants were also given the task during the Qualtrics survey of completing a risk aversion scale. They were asked a series of questions and drew from their own experience on a risk

aversion scale. This particular risk aversion scale might determine if the series of questions asked did impact their responses in a certain way.

We also used t-tests to determine whether there was an influence between whether work experience and being raised in a good household have a factor in a person blowing the whistle. If there was an influence between these two independent factors, there should be no evidence that the means differed significantly from zero. This analysis demonstrated that amongst the external reporting dependent variables and the internal reporting dependent variables, the differences did not differ significantly from zero. There is little to no evidence suggesting that the two independent variables we are currently testing do not influence participant response, or participants may have had trouble adopting the role of Casey in the particular hypothetical scenario. Therefore, we must focus our analysis on third-person participant responses.

Hypothesis Testing

The first hypothesis in this research was that good morals and work experience influence a person to blow the whistle. For example, the p-value for a new hire versus experienced employment and mentioning of a good household versus no mentioning good household, on question 6 of the survey, the value was 1.809. This indicates that the value is not significant. Thus there was no predisposition between the experience of work and the mentioning of good versus no good household. The results overall did show it did not influence people's propensity to blow the whistle.

Conclusion

Overall, whistleblowing can be influenced by a multitude of factors. Some are beyond our control. The two independent variables demonstrated that they did not impact a person's propensity to blow the whistle. According to the most recent National Business Ethics Survey conducted by the Ethics Resource Center (2013), they reported that of the 41 percent of workers who witnessed employee misconduct at work, only 63 percent reported these incidents.

In conclusion, many variables might influence a person's propensity to blow the whistle.

Unfortunately, my two independent variables did not affect a person's predisposition to blow the whistle over the other. Sometimes, we have to study more and find specific variables influencing a person's ability to blow the whistle.

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Estimated Marginal Means of 6) If you were in Casey's position, how likely is it that you would report this fraud through XYZ's internal reporting channel?

4. new hire vs experienced hire * mention of good household vs no good household

Dependent Variable: 6) If you were in Casey's position, how likely is it that you would report this fraud through

new hire vs experienced hire	mention of good household vs no good household	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
new hire	no mention of good household	5.545	.534	4.471	6.619
	mention of good household	5.700	.560	4.574	6.826
experienced hire	no mention of good household	5.500	.473	4.548	6.452
	mention of good household	5.533	.457	4.614	6.453

California State University, Fullerton Research Study Consent Form

Study Title: The Propensity of Workers to Blow the Whistle Based on Multiple Factors

Protocol Number: HSR-20-21-236

Researchers: Edward Lynch, Assistant Professor at Cal State University Fullerton/Department of Accounting; Annie Luu-Accounting and University Honors Undergraduate Student

You are being asked to take part in a research study carried out by Annie Luu alongside my mentor Professor Edward Lynch. This consent form explains the research study and your part in it if you decide to join the study. Please read this form carefully, taking as much time as you need. Ask the researcher to explain anything you don't understand. You can decide not to join the study. If you join the study, you can change your mind later and leave the study at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of services or benefits if you decide to not take part in the study.

What is this study about?

The purpose of this study is to determine why some workers decide to blow the whistle, while others are afraid or remain quiet about the things that they saw. This study will seek to answer the propensity of workers of blowing the whistle, based on factors, such as inexperienced versus experienced worker, religious upbringings, along with honesty scale and some demographics. These factors will be given randomly per student, and by measuring it, we will get a better sense of whether or not these factors do play a role in workers propensity to blow the whistle. Asking students, particularly accounting students is significant, because many of them, after college are entering the workforce, where most likely they will encounter scenarios, of whether or not they must blow the whistle. The purpose of this study is to determine hypothetical scenarios along with these factors, of whether or not, they do have a role in workers' blowing the whistle, and if they do play a role, how will we address these issues, in making sure that workers are not afraid of blowing the whistle on future incidents. Many of the students here at California State Fullerton, particularly accounting students, will enter the workforce soon and we desire to have their opinions heard through the gathering of the survey to determine the future of the workforce, and whether or not they will blow the whistle and expose the company of wrongdoing.

Taking a part in this survey will not be longer than 20 minutes. You cannot participate if you are not a CSUF student nor an accounting student.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

If you take part in the study, you will be asked to answer 30 survey questions regarding a tax scenario.

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

Participants will be compensated with extra credit for participating in this study. Furthermore, participants should know they have helped further research in accounting by participating in this study.

Are there any risks to me if I am in this study?

There are no foreseeable risks in this protocol. No personally identifiable data will be collected from participants (e.g., names, contact information, etc.).

Will my information be kept anonymous or confidential? The data for this study is being collected anonymously. Neither the researcher nor anyone else will be able to link data to you. The results from this study will be published or presented at professional meetings. The data from this study will be kept indefinitely and will be used for future research, presentations or publications.

Are there any costs or payments for being in this study?

There are no costs to participate in this study.

Who can I talk to if I have questions?

If you have questions about this study or the information in this form, please contact Edward Lynch at 657-278-8521 or elynch@fullerton.edu. If you have questions about your rights as a research participant, or would like to report a concern or complaint about this study, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719, or e-mail irb@fullerton.edu

What are my rights as a research study volunteer? Your participation in this research study is completely voluntary. You may choose not to be a part of this study. There will be no penalty to you if you choose not to take part. You may choose not to answer specific questions or to stop participating at any time.

Do you agree to participate in the survey?

The survey can be accessed by clicking YES below and then clicking the double arrow button (>>) to the lower right. By clicking YES you are indicating that you are at least 18 years of age, an Accounting major, and a CSUF student and have decided to participate having read the information provided above.

Yes

No

XYZ CASE (Version 1)

XYZ Manufacturing Inc. (XYZ) is an international consumer products manufacturing company. Founded in 1986, XYZ employs 3,000 people and trades on the New York Stock Exchange. As a publicly traded company, XYZ is required to file a quarterly report (10Q) and an annual report (10K) with the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC).

Casey Greenshade is a staff analyst, that was recently hired in the accounting department at XYZ.

Casey's responsibilities include the monthly reconciling of accounts, booking journal entries to the general ledger, and preparing internal reports. Casey is supervised by an accounting manager, who in turn reports to the director of financial reporting, and ultimately to the chief financial officer (CFO).

Employee financial interests are closely aligned with XYZ's business success because:

- The majority of the employees' retirement funds are reinvested in the company's stock
- The annual bonus for employees is based on current XYZ profits.

Recently, Casey discovered that his supervisor reduced XYZ's taxable income by diverting sales to foreign subsidiaries to avoid paying taxes in the U.S. This action is considered fraudulent under section 7206 of the Internal Revenue Code (IRC). Casey knows that there is a chance that this fraud may be detected. Therefore, he is considering whether or not he should report the fraud. Perpetrators of fraud face the risk of job loss, possible fines, and potential prison time should the fraud be discovered by the IRS. However, he knows there is a chance that penalties imposed by the IRS may be reduced for individuals who voluntarily provide information.

Per Section 7623 of the IRC, whistleblowers who provide original information to the IRS regarding tax noncompliance are eligible for monetary rewards. Specifically, whistleblowers can receive 15-30% of the proceeds if their information leads to the IRS imposing monetary sanctions that exceed \$2,000,000. Casey is certain this case would result in sanctions that meet the IRS threshold for reward compensation. However, potential rewards are significantly less or nonexistent if the whistleblower is determined to be the primary perpetrator of the fraudulent act.

Whistleblowers could alternatively report the fraud internally to XYZ's fraud hotline. Per Section 301 of the Sarbanes-Oxley Act, publicly traded companies are required to provide an anonymous and confidential internal fraud reporting channel for employees. Reporting internally could result in the fraud being addressed internally and could potentially avoid any negative publicity for XYZ.

Thus, Casey ultimately has three choices: not to report, to report internally, or to report externally to the IRS. Although Casey knows that if he decides to report the wrongdoing there may be negative repercussions such as retaliation.

XYZ CASE (Version 2)

XYZ Manufacturing Inc. (XYZ) is an international consumer products manufacturing company. Founded in 1986, XYZ employs 3,000 people and trades on the New York Stock Exchange. As a publicly traded company, XYZ is required to file a quarterly report (10Q) and an annual report (10K) with the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC).

Casey Greenshade is a staff analyst, that was recently hired in the accounting department at XYZ. **[Casey was raised in a good household, that emphasized good moral values and honesty.]**

Casey's responsibilities include the monthly reconciling of accounts, booking journal entries to the general ledger, and preparing internal reports. Casey is supervised by an accounting manager, who in turn reports to the director of financial reporting, and ultimately to the chief financial officer (CFO).

Employee financial interests are closely aligned with XYZ's business success because:

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XYZ CASE (Version 3)

XYZ Manufacturing Inc. (XYZ) is an international consumer products manufacturing company. Founded in 1986, XYZ employs 3,000 people and trades on the New York Stock Exchange. As a publicly traded company, XYZ is required to file a quarterly report (10Q) and an annual report (10K) with the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC).

Casey Greenshade is a staff analyst, that has **eight years of experience** in the accounting department at XYZ.

Casey's responsibilities include the monthly reconciling of accounts, booking journal entries to the general ledger, and preparing internal reports. Casey is supervised by an accounting manager, who in turn reports to the director of financial reporting, and ultimately to the chief financial officer (CFO).

Employee financial interests are closely aligned with XYZ's business success because:

- The majority of the employees' retirement funds are reinvested in the company's stock
- The annual bonus for employees is based on current XYZ profits.

Recently, Casey discovered that his supervisor reduced XYZ's taxable income by diverting sales to foreign subsidiaries to avoid paying taxes in the U.S. This action is considered fraudulent under section 7206 of the Internal Revenue Code (IRC). Casey knows that there is a chance that this fraud may be detected. Therefore, he is considering whether or not he should report the fraud. Perpetrators of fraud face the risk of job loss, possible fines, and potential prison time should the fraud be discovered by the IRS. However, he knows there is a chance that penalties imposed by the IRS may be reduced for individuals who voluntarily provide information.

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sanctions that exceed \$2,000,000. Casey is certain this case would result in sanctions that meet the IRS threshold for reward compensation. However, potential rewards are significantly less or nonexistent if the whistleblower is determined to be the primary perpetrator of the fraudulent act.

Whistleblowers could alternatively report the fraud internally to XYZ's fraud hotline. Per Section 301 of the Sarbanes-Oxley Act, publicly traded companies are required to provide an anonymous and confidential internal fraud reporting channel for employees. Reporting internally could result in the fraud being addressed internally and could potentially avoid any negative publicity for XYZ.

Thus, Casey ultimately has three choices: not to report, to report internally, or to report externally to the IRS. Although Casey knows that if he decides to report the wrongdoing there may be negative repercussions such as retaliation.

PLEASE ANSWER THE QUESTIONS ON THE FOLLOWING PAGES REGARDING THE CASE IN THE ORDER LISTED. DO NOT GO BACK AND CHANGE YOUR ANSWERS. YOU MAY REFER BACK TO THE CASE MATERIALS IF YOU WISH.

XYZ CASE (Version 4)

XYZ Manufacturing Inc. (XYZ) is an international consumer products manufacturing company. Founded in 1986, XYZ employs 3,000 people and trades on the New York Stock Exchange. As a publicly traded company, XYZ is required to file a quarterly report (10Q) and an annual report (10K) with the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC).

Casey Greenshade is a staff analyst, that has **eight years of experience** in the accounting department at XYZ. **[Casey was raised in a good household, that emphasized good moral values and honesty.]**

Casey's responsibilities include the monthly reconciling of accounts, booking journal entries to the general ledger, and preparing internal reports. Casey is supervised by an accounting manager, who in turn reports to the director of financial reporting, and ultimately to the chief financial officer (CFO).

Employee financial interests are closely aligned with XYZ's business success because:

- The majority of the employees' retirement funds are reinvested in the company's stock
- The annual bonus for employees is based on current XYZ profits.

Recently, Casey discovered that his supervisor reduced XYZ's taxable income by diverting sales to foreign subsidiaries to avoid paying taxes in the U.S. This action is considered fraudulent under section 7206 of the Internal Revenue Code (IRC). Casey knows that there is a chance that

this fraud may be detected. Therefore, he is considering whether or not he should report the fraud. Perpetrators of fraud face the risk of job loss, possible fines, and potential prison time should the fraud be discovered by the IRS. However, he knows there is a chance that penalties imposed by the IRS may be reduced for individuals who voluntarily provide information.

Per Section 7623 of the IRC, whistleblowers who provide original information to the IRS regarding tax noncompliance are eligible for monetary rewards. Specifically, whistleblowers can receive 15-30% of the proceeds if their information leads to the IRS imposing monetary sanctions that exceed \$2,000,000. Casey is certain this case would result in sanctions that meet the IRS threshold for reward compensation. However, potential rewards are significantly less or nonexistent if the whistleblower is determined to be the primary perpetrator of the fraudulent act.

Whistleblowers could alternatively report the fraud internally to XYZ's fraud hotline. Per Section 301 of the Sarbanes-Oxley Act, publicly traded companies are required to provide an anonymous and confidential internal fraud reporting channel for employees. Reporting internally could result in the fraud being addressed internally and could potentially avoid any negative publicity for XYZ.

Thus, Casey ultimately has three choices: not to report, to report internally, or to report externally to the IRS. Although Casey knows that if he decides to report the wrongdoing there may be negative repercussions such as retaliation.

PLEASE ANSWER THE QUESTIONS ON THE FOLLOWING PAGES REGARDING THE CASE IN THE ORDER LISTED. DO NOT GO BACK AND CHANGE YOUR ANSWERS. YOU MAY REFER BACK TO THE CASE MATERIALS IF YOU WISH.

1. [Yes or No] Did the case say **Casey was recently hired**?

_____ Yes
_____ No

2. [Yes or No] Did the case mention that **Casey came from a good household that emphasized good moral values and honesty**?

_____ Yes
_____ No

For the following questions, **please select** the number or option that corresponds with your answer.

3. How likely do you think it is that **Casey** will report this fraud to the **IRS**?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Extremely Unlikely	Moderately Unlikely	Somewhat Unlikely	Not Sure	Somewhat Likely	Moderately Likely	Extremely Likely

4. If you were in Casey's position, how likely is that **you** would report this fraud to the **IRS?**

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Extremely Unlikely	Moderately Unlikely	Somewhat Unlikely	Not Sure	Somewhat Likely	Moderately Likely	Extremely Likely

5. How likely do you think it is that **Casey** will report this fraud through XYZ's **internal reporting channel?**

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Extremely Unlikely	Moderately Unlikely	Somewhat Unlikely	Not Sure	Somewhat Likely	Moderately Likely	Extremely Likely

6. If you were in Casey's position, how likely is it that **you** would report this fraud through XYZ's **internal reporting channel?**

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Extremely Unlikely	Moderately Unlikely	Somewhat Unlikely	Not Sure	Somewhat Likely	Moderately Likely	Extremely Likely

7. Please indicate how serious you perceive this fraudulent act to be?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Extremely Unlikely	Moderately Unlikely	Somewhat Unlikely	Not Sure	Somewhat Likely	Moderately Likely	Extremely Likely

8. Please indicate how much the perceived threat of retaliation impacted your reporting decisions in the questions above?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Extremely Unlikely	Moderately Unlikely	Somewhat Unlikely	Not Sure	Somewhat Likely	Moderately Likely	Extremely Likely

9. Please indicate how important you considered the IRS financial reward as being in your decision to report above?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Extremely Unlikely	Moderately Unlikely	Somewhat Unlikely	Not Sure	Somewhat Likely	Moderately Likely	Extremely Likely

10. How much did the potential for a reduced sentence influence your decision to report?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Extremely Unlikely	Moderately Unlikely	Somewhat Unlikely	Not Sure	Somewhat Likely	Moderately Likely	Extremely Likely

11. In your opinion, how trustworthy is the IRS?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Extremely Unlikely	Moderately Unlikely	Somewhat Unlikely	Not Sure	Somewhat Likely	Moderately Likely	Extremely Likely

12. In your opinion, does it matter if Casey came from a good household that emphasized good morals and honesty?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
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Extremely Unlikely	Moderately Unlikely	Somewhat Unlikely	Not Sure	Somewhat Likely	Moderately Likely	Extremely Likely
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Risk Aversion scale from Blair and Webb (2006) – 6 Questions

13. For each of the following statements, please indicate your likelihood of engaging in each activity or behavior. Provide a rating from **1 to 7**, using the following scale:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Extremely Unlikely	Moderately Unlikely	Somewhat Unlikely	Not Sure	Somewhat Likely	Moderately Likely	Extremely Likely

_____ Betting a day's income at the horse races.

_____ Investing 10% of your annual income in a moderate growth mutual fund.

_____ Betting a day's income at a high-stake poker game.

_____ Investing 5% of your annual income in a very speculative stock.

_____ Betting a day's income at a sporting event.

_____ Investing 10% of your annual income in a new business venture.

14. Please indicate your gender: _____ Male _____ Female _____ Other

15. What is your age? _____

16. How many years of professional work experience do you have? _____

17. What degree program are you in at CSUF (e.g., MBA)? _____

18. As part of your work experience, have you ever discovered a person of greater authority engaging in questionable behavior? _____ Yes _____ No

Honesty/Humility Scale from Brink et al. (2018) and Lee and Ashton (2004) – 15 Questions

19. I would be tempted to buy stolen property if I were financially tight.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
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Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Not Sure	Somewhat Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree
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20. I would never accept a bribe, even if it were very large.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Not Sure	Somewhat Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree

21. If I knew that I could never get caught, I would be willing to steal a million dollars.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Not Sure	Somewhat Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree

22. Please select "Strongly Agree" below.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Not Sure	Somewhat Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree

23. I'd be tempted to use counterfeit money, if I were sure I could get away with it.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Not Sure	Somewhat Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree

24. I would like to live in a very expensive, high-class neighborhood.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Not Sure	Somewhat Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree

25. Having a lot of money is not especially important to me.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Not Sure	Somewhat Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree

26. I would like to be seen driving around in a very expensive car.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Not Sure	Somewhat Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree

27. I would get a lot of pleasure from owning expensive luxury goods.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Not Sure	Somewhat Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree

28. If I want something from a person I dislike, I will act very nicely toward that person in order to get it.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Not Sure	Somewhat Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree

29. I wouldn't use flattery to get a raise or promotion at work, even if I thought it would succeed.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Not Sure	Somewhat Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree

30. I wouldn't pretend to like someone just to get that person to do favors for me.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Not Sure	Somewhat Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree

31. I am an ordinary person who is no better than others.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Not Sure	Somewhat Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree

32. I wouldn't want people to treat me as though I were superior to them.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Not Sure	Somewhat Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree

33. I want people to know that I am an important person of high status.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Not Sure	Somewhat Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree

34. I think that I am entitled to more respect than the average person is.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Not Sure	Somewhat Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree